

A Self-Sovereign Digital Wallet for Sustainable Construction

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Abstract

The advent of Web3, Construction 4.0, and the transition to BIM Level 3 has ushered in a wave of innovative technologies that call for a fresh approach to establishing secure connections and safeguarding sensitive information. This shift demands a departure from traditional paper-based identity methods to embrace digital alternatives. In this context, self-sovereign identity (SSI) emerges as a pivotal solution. SSI empowers individuals and entities within the construction industry to maintain full control over their digital identities, guaranteeing privacy, security, and seamless authentication across diverse platforms and systems. Through the adoption of SSI, the construction industry embarks on a transformative journey, empowering its stakeholders to confidently navigate the intricate terrain of contemporary construction processes and technologies. This study advocates for the creation of a self-sovereign digital wallet tailored specifically for the construction sector, harnessing the capabilities of Decentralized Identifiers and Verifiable Credentials. This digital wallet serves as a highly secure repository for all building-related data, ensuring both the integrity and accessibility of this valuable information. Our system proposal places particular emphasis on two key roles within this ecosystem: Contractors and Construction Companies. Each verifiable credential is intricately linked to a unique DID, securely stored in an on-chain registry.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/9arBiFQovKA>

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